

Magma Dynamics and Cooling in Sub-volcanic intrusions: Insights on eruption potential from Finite Element Modelling

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List of run models of the paper “**Magma Dynamics and Cooling in Sub-volcanic intrusions: Insights on eruption potential from Finite Element Modelling**”.

Model	DOI
<i>instant_conduction</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19564657
<i>instant_convection</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19126378
<i>intruded_1month</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18849502
<i>intruded_1year</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20341026
<i>intruded_12years</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20341043
<i>intruded_25years</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20341077
<i>intruded_127years</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20341122